

Reprexbase: Trustworthy Data Enrichment Workflow

Sample publication based on the Fényképészek és fényképésműtermek Magyarországon (1840-1945) database for a reviewable data enrichment and dissemination process with the Reprexbase system

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In this sample publication we would like to show, how you can enrich the database of the monograph *Fényképészek és fényképésműtermek Magyarországon (1840-1945) adattára* [Photographers and photographic studios in the Hungarian Kingdom (1840-1945)] with easy-to-review and verify new data. We will provide several examples in two scenarios. The first will help the to establish a link to existing scientific databases with the use of linking to authority files (name spaces.) The second scenario enriches the database with knowledge held in primary sources.

We provide a simple revision table for the information that we would like to have reviewed at Section .

This translation is a slightly contextualised version of the [Hungarian text](#) of this sample publication.

Glossary

namespace : *célja, hogy az egyes entitásokat önmagukkal azonos, összetéveszthetetlen egységként regisztrálja, úgy, hogy az entitáshoz tartozó névváltozatokat is rögzítse. (Bánki, Zsolt, Záros, Zsolt, and Szatucsek, Zoltán 2023)* needs translation

authority file: An authority file is a list that contains the authoritative way to reference people, places, things, or concepts, usually as a heading or numeric identifier.

Magyar Nemzeti Névtér: The beta version of a Hungarian national name space in operation since 2019.

VIAF: Virtual International Authority file combines multiple name authority files into a single OCLC-hosted name authority service.

Linking to Authorities

The aim of a national name authority or the international VIAF system is the identification of unique named entities (persons, corporate bodies and geographical locations) to enable data and knowledge linking across library, archival, museum, rights management and other applications without ambiguity. It enables a researcher to find data about **Kalmár, Péter**, the imperial and royal court photographer (1850-1900) without accidentally referring to another person named Kalmár, Péter.

Connecting a database with a name authority can quickly improve a database and help enriching it with interoperable knowledge sources. In this example, we show how the researchers of the Hungarian National Museum can enrich the database of the monograph *Fényképészek és fényképezőműtermek Magyarországon (1840-1945) adattára* [Photographers and photographic studios in the Hungarian Kingdom (1840-1945)]. This database, first published in 1997, and constantly improved in the last 27 years, is the authoritative scientific source of information on the early photography of the former Hungarian Kingdom, including the entire territory of modern Slovakia, and a part of Croatia, Romania, Ukraine, with further data on Austria and nearby countries.

We show how our **Reprexbase** system can help the data linking, enriching, review and publication workflow. In our example, we connect named entities in the database of the Hungarian National Museum (which is available online, see later links) to the namespace of the Petőfi Literary Museum (PIM), the Hungarian national name space operated by the national library, and VIAF. Connecting to VIAF can be a first step to new finds with the help of the **New York Public Library Photographers' Identities Database**, which is used by many galleries and museums. (We have found with its help likely unknown works of the photographers of the Hungarian database.)

Linking the database to name spaces: knowledge import links

Connecting the name spaces as authoritative sources is based on personal data. For example, in case of **Kalmár, Péter** the Hungarian national name space has a record [849673](#), as well as the PIM museum [PIM1858288](#). The second authority file also contains a bibliographical source for the knowledge, a monograph (Farkas 2005, p247). We can import the birth year and death year with a reference for possible revision in the literature (1850, and circa 1900). Importing this knowledge into the database does not only help us to know more about Kalmár, but helps making inferences about his photographic studios. For example, we have record of an atelier in the same house where he claimed in 1888 to have his on studio, but under a different name, in 1901. Székely & Co had a photographic atelier at Andrassy út 29, which is the same address that Kalmár used in his advertisements. The novel information of the year of death in 1900 makes it likely (but does not proves) that his heirs sold the atelier to Székely & Co. in 1901.

So, whenever we find a named entity in a naming authority such as VIAF, PIM, MNN, we try to establish a link between the authority file of the named entity and our database, so that we can import further knowledge from other reliable sources who also use the same name authority for identifying their persons or things (in this case, photographers.)

For the Hungarian National Museum, we suggest the use of the following links to authority files in their database:

Table 1: Suggested named entity linking (deceased persons)

Name	dates	VIAF	ISNI	PIM	MNN	Wikidata QID
Funk Pál	1894.01.31- 1974.12.13	731907722	0000000078716915	PIM41000	665032	Q769412
Baktay Ervin	1890.06.24- 1963.05.07	224120	108642858	PIM42930	671463	Q652083
Balogh Rudolf	1879.09.07- 1944.10.09	7678311	78214851	PIM43681	664597	Q789672

Linking the database to name spaces: knowledge export link

We are exporting knowledge when we have an authoritative scientific or industry source, but the name space authority, such as the national name space or VIAF has no record of a named entity (such as a person, a corporate body or a geographical location.) Sharing the reliable information with the authority control body is helpful, because other knowledge organisations (museums, archives, libraries, registers) may have already shared knowledge about the person in question. To link up with new knowledge source the first step is establishing the equivalence of the name in another source, for example, in the **New York Public Library Photographers' Identities Database**.

In our example, we are suggesting the Hungarian National Museum experts to provide the following names for the national namespace (at the national library):

- Emellett rengeteg olyan nevet tartalmaz még az adatbázis, akiknek nincsen ismert külső azonosítója, viszont dátumjaik és fotóműhelyeik helye ismert, ami segíti a beazonosítást. Pl. [Beller, Rezső \(1877-1949k.\)](#), akinek a budapesti Király utcában volt műhelye. Az alábbi táblázatban feltüntetünk még pár ilyen embert, referenciaként a fotótár által megosztott [budapest](#) és [hungary](#) táblázatok szolgálnak mellettük egy szám mutatja a táblázat adott sorát:

Table 2: Suggested entries to the national name space (we can make further suggestions!)

Name	Dates	Database (table, entry)
Braun Menyhért	1850-1923	budapest 159,160
Beller Rezső	1877-1949k	budapest 100,101,102,103,105
Becske Adolf	1850-1923	hungary 147
Vajda Dóri	1880-1944	hungary 1990
Adler Leopold	1848-1929	hungary 20
Badovinsky Pál	1851-1937	budapest 44

Adding new knowledge from primary sources

We have edited the database of the monograph *Fényképészek és fényképésműtermek Magyarországon (1840-1945)* database into several datasets, one of them contains the photographic studios or ateliers as workplaces (they can also be viewed as corporate bodies of a working collective in the studio.)

For easier revision and viewing, we created further, small sub-datasets based on geographical or timewise subsetting (for example, for the town of Vác, or for the time period before the unification of Budapest the Pest side only.)

In our example, Péter Kalmár imperial and royal court photographer and painter announces the opening of his new atelier, and we want to add this information to our knowledge base. The issue 46 of the 2nd volume Váci Hírlap dated 1888-11-11 (with spelling at the time, Váczi Hírlap) ran an advertisement where the founder announced that he was about to open personally for the public his atelier on the main square (currently named: Square of 15 March), in the yard of the local savings bank on 16 November 1888. (Kalmár 1888).

VÁCZI HÍRLAP. November hó 11.

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kká jövőre
yhangulag

terti titkár
n időzött,
ztított szó-
azok adójá-
leszállítása

LATOK

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működik a
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tet nyert,
hó 1-től
az állandó
ményes je-
szövetkezet
megkezdése
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sztésére és
zkezdéseket
vja a vár

— T. F. Dömös. Miért nem vette igénybe a kedvezményt ez alkalommal is már? A felesleget előjegyeztük a jövő évnegyedre. — V. V. Igaza van, ha a szerkesztőséget a közönség szolgájaként is mondja. Szolgálni akarjuk azt mert csak is úgy érhetjük el, hogy működésünket elismeréssel fogadják. Nem fogunk ki-mélni semmi fáradságot, hogy a belénk helyzett bizalomnak megfelelhessünk; de a mi közönségünk még nem ébredt annak tudatára, hogy nekünk sokkal több alkalmunk van mindenüvé „bepillantani”, mint az egyeseknek. Elkövetkezik ennek is az ideje. — P. A. Megkíséreltük, mint ezt mai számunkból láthatja. Az eredményre magunk is kíváncsiak vagyunk. — G. A. Budapest. „Az orvos növendék élményeit” már kiszedettük volna, ha a kézirat kezeink közt lenne. Talán meg lehetne egy kicsit sürgetni.

NYILT-TÉR.*

Azon egyént, ki hozzám szeptember hó első napjaiban névtelen levelet irt saját érdekében újból is figyelmeztetem, hogy hivatalos helyiségemben felkeressen.

Meiszner Ede
közgyám.

* E rovart alatt közlöttekért nem vállal felelős.

Van szerencsém a nagyérdemű közönség becses tudomására hozni, miszerint számos felszólítás folytán **Vácson, a főtéren, a takarékpénztár udvarában** egy állandó, teljesen felszerelt, éjszakai világítással bíró

FESTŐI ÉS FÉNYKÉPÉSZI MŰTERMET

építtettem, melyet csötörtökön, folyó hó 16 ikán személyesen fogok megnyitni.

Főüzletem, Budapestben, Andrassy-ut 29. szám alatt, általános ismert jó hírnévvel bíró és ez feleslegessé teszi a további reclamat részemről. Annál is inkább, minékutána legfőbb törekvésem oda irányul, hogy itt Vácson is ép oly kiváló, jó és műlisséssel bíró képeket szolgáltat-sak ki, mint a fővárosban.

A kiadott képek jóságáról és finomságáról kezeskedem, minékutána sikertelen képek jó hírnevem érdekében ki nem adatnak.

A műterem 16-ától, vasárnap f. hó 19-én át nyitva marad és azon időn túl pedig **heteként szombat, vasárnap és ünnepi napokon** át nyitva áll a n. é. közönség rendelkezésére. — A felvételek eszközlésével évek hosszú során át nálam működő üzletvezetőmet bízom meg és kérem, öt teljes bizalmukkal szerencsélteni. **A legborultabb idő is alkalmas a felvételekre.** — A műterem fűttetik.

A takarékpénztárnál kiállított képgyűjteményemet becses figyelmükbe ajánlván, maradtam tisztelettel

1-6

Kalmár Péter, udvari fényképész és festő.

Figure 1: Váci Hírlap, vol 2, issue 46, page 152.

- Our primary task is to record the information of the inception date of this atelier in Vác.
- In the same advertisement he mentions his main atelier at Budapest, Andrassy Avenue 29. Our secondary objective is to add this corroborating information about the Budapest atelier to that data page.
- We also want to connect the ateliers via the work location relationship to Péter Kalmár (the deceased person) and his corporate body.

The database of the monograph *Fényképészek és fényképszemlétermek Magyarországon (1840-1945)* is aware of a photographic studio at Andrassy Ave 29. (Székely és Társa, i.e., Székely & Co), but Kalmár had worked here earlier. Because the house was built in 1884, and we have a published verso from 1887 in the online collection of Fortepan, and the advertisement mentions this work location in 1888, we place the inception date at 1880s. We do not know (but it is rather likely) that Székely & Co used the same part of this building. However, it is certain that the corporate body of the atelier of P. Kalmár is different from the corporate body of Székely & Co. A further notable connection is that the famous future photographer, Manó Mai did his apprenticeship in the studio of Péter Kalmár.

Because Péter Kalmár already has an entry in the national name space, we connect his record with the name space record as an authority file, and import the year of birth and death from the authority file.

Recording data in Orosháza for review

Béla Ábrahám is known in the original monograph as an early 20th century photographer based in Békéscsaba (Southeastern Hungary). His photographic studio was recorded in the original database, but no birth or death date, or any other personal information that would allow this name to be disambiguated from other people named Béla Ábrahám. So we made a small research and we would like to add the following information about him.

The daily newspaper *Orosházi Napilap* publishes an interview on 23 August 1964 with Béla Ábrahám, who became an intern at a photographic studio at the age of 13 and a half years, dating it 3 months before the murder of Archduke Franz Ferdinand (28 June 1914). This means that Béla Ábrahám was 13 in 1913, placing his year of birth in 1900.

In the same interview, he is talking about being active at the age of 64 (in line with being born in the second half of 1900), and he also mentions having won a Golden Palm prize in the photographic exhibition at Oradea in 1941 (Ternyák 1964).

On 1964-10-18 the *Békés Megyei Népújság* (county newspaper) published an announcement on behalf of the family for those who expressed their condolences to the family at his burial ('Gyászjelentés a Békés Megyei Népújságban [Obituary in the Békés Megyei Népújság]' 1964). This places the year of death at 1964.

As we have not seen actual dates, birth or death certificates, we qualify this information as approximate. We believe that the year is correct but we have no exact dates.

Review and reliability

In our knowledge base and graph database we have created an [authority control status](#) label class with the following labelling instances.

- [controlled information by domain expert](#): an authoritative body or expert has reviewed the data. For example: [controlled by MNM Történeti Fotótár](#), [controlled by MAFOT Hungarian Photographic History Association](#) (These are just examples, no such review took yet place.)
- [waiting for domain expert control](#): we have asked a peer or authoritative review from a relevant expert in the field.
- [controlled information processing](#), for example, *controlled by Reprex*, means that we have taken the data in a professional data pipeline from a reliable authoritative source. The data ingestion may require review, however, if our pipeline is not broken, the data itself is reliable. Random review of the data is advisable, but the data should be the same as data in the authoritative register or scientific source. The data pipeline also provides data provenience.

Review Data Table

Table 3: Summary of the new primary information

Link	Description	New data for review
Q1085	atelier “Kalmár Péter” (Vác) inception: 1888. 11. 16. source: Váci Hírlap, 1888. 11. 11. used by: Kalmár, Péter	
Q1122	atelier “Kalmár Péter” (Andrássy Ave 29)	inception: 1880s source: Váci Hírlap, 1888. 11. 11.
Q1123	Kalmár, Péter	description: imperial and royal court photographer Biographical data imported from authority files: Magyar Nemzeti Névtér ID: 849673, PIM1858288
Q1112	Ábrahám, Béla	Biographical data Year of birth: 1900 Source: Orosházi Napilap, vol 9, issue 98, 1964. 08. 23. Year of death: 1964 Source: Békés Megyei Népszerűség, 245. sz., 1964. október 18.
Q1125	Photographic Studio of Béla Ábrahám	Link with the personal record of Ábrahám, Béla.

Suggested entries for the national library into the national namespace

Table 4: Suggested entries to the national name space (we can make further suggestions!)

name	dates	database (table, entry ID)
Braun Menyhért	1850-1923	budapest 159,160
Beller Rezső	1877-1949k	budapest 100,101,102,103,105
Becske Adolf	1850-1923	hungary 147
Vajda Dóri	1880-1944	hungary 1990
Adler Leopold	1848-1929	hungary 20
Badovinsky Pál	1851-1937	budapest 44

Bánki, Zsolt, Záros, Zsolt, and Szatucsek, Zoltán. 2023. ‘A névterek mint a hiteles tudás forrásai: A Nemzeti Levéltár földrajzi névtér projektjének bemutatása’. Tudományos és Műszaki Tájékoztatás. <https://doi.org/10.3311/tmt.13273>.

Farkas, Zsuzsa. 2005. *Festőfény: Festő-fényképészek 1840-1880*. Kecskemét, Hungary: Magyar Fotográfiai Múzeum.

‘Gyászjelentés a Békés Megyei Népújságban [Obituary in the Békés Megyei Népújság]’. 1964. Arcanum. https://adt.arcanum.com/hu/view/BekesMegyeiNepujzag_ADT_1964_10/?query=%22%C3%81brah%C3%A1m+B%C3%A9la%22+AND+%22B%C3%A9k%C3%A9scsaba%22&pg=137&layout=s.

Kalmár, Péter. 1888. ‘Hirdetés a Váci Hirlapban [Advertisement in Váci Hirlap]’. Hungaricana. https://library.hungaricana.hu/hu/view/VaciHirlap_1888/?pg=159&layout=s.

Ternyák, Péter. 1964. ‘‘Barátságos arcot kérek...’’. Arcanum. https://adt.arcanum.com/hu/view/OroshaziHirlap_1964-3/?pg=212&layout=s.